

CORRELATION OF VITAMIN B12, FOLIC ACID AND IRON DEFICIENCIES ON CLASS PERFORMANCE AND GENERAL FITNESS AMONG SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN

Sadaf Ilyas^{*1}, Rooma Adalat², Zainab Khalid³, Yamina Anwar⁴, Saba Manzoor⁵, Nazim Tufail⁶, Saima Sana Ullah⁷

^{*1,2,3,4,5,7}Department of Zoology, University of the Sialkot, Sialkot, Pakistan

⁶Department of Mathematics, University of Management and technology, Sialkot, Pakistan

¹sadaf.ilyas@uskt.edu.pk, ⁵saba.manzoor@uskt.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Sadaf Ilyas

Abstract

Micronutrient deficiencies such as vitamin B12, folic acid, and iron are most prevalent in Pakistan due to less outdoor activities that affect the cognitive and physical development of school-going children. The current study aimed to explore the association and correlation of these deficiencies with class performance and general fitness among school going children of district Sialkot. The study included 300 school-going children aged 10-12 years with an equal distribution of boys and girls. Data was collected from various schools of district Sialkot schools. Approximately 5ml of blood was drawn from each participant and the levels of vitamin B12, folic acid and iron were analyzed. Students found to be deficient in these micronutrients were considered as experimental group while those having no deficiency were considered as control group. Moreover, classroom performance and physical fitness tests were conducted to assess the effects of these deficiencies on class performance and general fitness of students. Class performance and general fitness were Positive correlation with micronutrient among school going children. Students exhibiting higher micronutrient deficiency led to poorer class performance. The current study emphasizes the need of community nutrition programs, public awareness campaigns and parental education to enhance academic performance, physical fitness, and long-term development of their children which contribute to Pakistan's socio-economic growth.

INTRODUCTION

Nutrition is a foundation of brain development and overall well-being throughout the life of an individual which influences growth and functioning at every stage of life. Adequate nutrition is essential during infancy and early childhood because it supports cognitive development and set the foundation of future learning and behavior of children (Rani et al., 2017). In adolescence proper nutrient intake especially B12, folic acid and iron become critical

for maintaining energy levels, concentration, and emotional stability in classroom because rapid physical and psychological changes occur during this period (Singh et al., 2023). In adulthood, nutrition continues to play a role in sustaining mental acuity and preventing chronic diseases hence emphasizes its lifelong significance. Malnutrition has long-term adverse effects on intellectual abilities and academic performance

among school aged children particularly during early childhood (Akubuilu et al., 2020).

Micronutrients such as vitamin B12, folic acid (FA) and iron are essential for normal growth and overall health of children even though they are required in small amounts. Deficiencies in these critical nutrients impair cognitive functioning which negatively affects classroom performance and physical fitness (Awasthi et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2023).

Students who regularly consume a diet rich in essential micronutrients e.g. vit B12, FA and iron tend to perform better academically. Particularly, those students who regularly eat breakfast rich in essential micronutrients show better classroom performance (Burrows et al., 2017). Insufficient micronutrients intake can lead to logical disabilities and other developmental problems in children (Banerjee et al., 2023).

Micronutrient deficiencies are often termed as "hidden hunger" which refers to a lack of vital vitamins and minerals in the diet of an individual, even when their caloric intake is sufficient. These deficiencies may not present immediate physical symptoms, making them harder to detect but they have profound effects on mental and physical development. For example, hidden hunger can impair cognitive functions, weaken the immune system and hinder physical growth which ultimately threatens the future potential of children (Bailey et al., 2015). A lack of dietary quality contributes to deficiencies in B12, FA, and iron resulting in poor academic outcomes and diminished physical health particularly in urban and rural populations (Evang et al., 2020). These deficiencies are implicated in developmental delays, intellectual disabilities and poor classroom performance throughout the world (Black et al., 2020).

Vitamin B12 is also known as cobalamin which is essential for DNA synthesis, RBCs formation and neurological function (Aygün et al., 2019). It plays a critical role in myelin sheath production, neurotransmitter synthesis and brain health which are vital for cognitive development and academic performance (Alfawaz et al., 2020). It is a water-soluble vitamin found naturally in animal

products and is crucial for human health (Green et al., 2017; Lam et al., 2017). Deficiencies in B12 can lead to neurological disorders, cognitive impairments and delayed growth which ultimately affects both academic performance and general fitness in children (Nawaz et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2021). Children with B12 deficiency often struggle with memory retention and exhibit lower problem-solving skills which are limiting their ability to excel academically. Furthermore, severe B12 deficiencies are associated with neurodevelopmental delays including difficulties in language acquisition and motor skills (Sahni, 2020; Hasbaoui et al., 2021). Folic acid is a synthetic form of vitamin B9 which is vital for DNA and RNA synthesis, cell division and the formation of red blood cells. It supports cognitive functions including learning, memory and mood regulation. It also plays a significant role in neurotransmitter synthesis (Liew, 2016). Naturally occurring form of folic acid is Folate. The term "folate" is derived from the Latin word folium means "leaf." Folic acid is converted into its active form tetrahydrofolate (THF) which serves as a coenzyme in various metabolic reactions in the human body (Mironenko, 2019).

FA also plays a critical role during pregnancy and early childhood development which influences neural tube formation and reduces the risks of developmental disorders (Kiani et al., 2022). Children having FA deficiency often experience learning disabilities, reduced physical activity levels and shorter attention span. Improved access to folate- rich diets has demonstrated marked improvements in cognitive scores and behavioral outcomes in school environment (Lam et al., 2017).

FA levels can also affect physical fitness, which is a crucial aspect of general health. Children who consume adequate amount of folate have higher levels of endurance and physical activity because it is essential for energy metabolism and muscular function (Smith et al., 2022). On the other hand, deficiencies may result in symptoms including weakened muscles, exhaustion and decreased physical activity which can further hinder a child's social and academic growth (Lee & Park, 2021). Furthermore, FA supports the immune

system, hence its deficiency has been associated with poorer physical stamina and increased susceptibility to infections in school going children (Crider et al., 2011; Huang et al., 2022). Iron is essential for human growth and health because it is required for various physiological and biochemical processes. It produces hemoglobin which carries oxygen from the lungs to tissues for cellular activity and energy generation (Vogt et al., 2021). Additionally, iron supports immune responses, enzyme functions and neurological development. Despite its importance, iron deficiency is the most prevalent nutritional shortfall globally, which particularly affects children in developing nations. This deficiency can significantly impact memory and physical performance of school-aged children who are undergoing critical stages of growth and learning (Leung et al., 2024).

Iron is vital for nerve growth and is essential for bodily functions. It is abundant in nature and crucial for all living organisms. It exists in two forms such as heme and non-heme iron. Heme iron is found in animal products like meat, eggs, shellfish and poultry which are highly bioavailable. Non-heme iron is present in plant-based foods and fortified products. It is less readily absorbed by the body (Sanz et al., 2008). Children taking insufficient folate throughout their critical developmental stages may suffer from speech and language problems, delayed motor skills and other long-term effects. It is important to ensure that children obtain enough FA during their early years because these developmental delays can impact social and emotional development in addition to academic performance (Alam, 2020).

Deficiencies in key micronutrients like folic acid, iron, and B12 are often associated with poor memory, learning difficulties, and reduced concentration. Developing nations, in particular, face high risks of B12 deficiencies, which contribute to poorer academic performance (Masalha et al., 2008; Smith et al., 2022). Child nutrition through school-based programs can be enhanced in Pakistan that include nutritious meals, regular health check-ups and education on nutrition which can lead to higher academic and

physical results. Collaboration among the government, private groups and schools can boost the success of these efforts. Proper nutrition not only benefits individual children but also contributes to national progress by reducing healthcare expenditures and increasing productivity. These nutritional gaps are addressed through targeted programs in maternal health, early childhood care and community awareness that can ensure a better future for children and maximize their potential that may contribute to the country's development.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study was an experimental cross-sectional investigation in which total 300 random students chosen from various schools of Sialkot, comprising of 150 boys and 150 girls were included in the study. The aim of the study is to evaluate the ratio of students who are suffering from these deficiencies also find the correlation of deficiency (iron, folic acid, and vitamin B12) with academic performance.

Additionally, also assess the correlation of each deficiency (iron, folic acid, and vitamin B12) with overall fitness. The study included only those students aged 10 to 12 years, apparently healthy (with a normal BMI) and whose parents gave written consent. While those students suffering from chronic diseases such as diabetes, hepatitis or tuberculosis excluded from the study. Additionally, students with a BMI lower than 12.5 were also excluded from the study. Students having multiple deficiencies are also excluded from the study.

2.1. Demographic and socioeconomic data

A questionnaire was developed for students and their parents to collect data on age, gender, medical history, daily diet, and socioeconomic status. The questionnaire included both multiple-choice and open-ended questions. Socioeconomic status was assessed using the Revised Kuppaswamy's Socioeconomic Scale, which evaluates monthly family income, education level, and the occupation of the head of the family. Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated manually

using the formula: BMI = weight (kg) / height (m²).

2.2. Blood sample collection

Blood samples were collected from the selected students during school hours by a trained phlebotomist. A 5 mL blood was drawn from each student, from the cubital vein using a sterilized syringe during school hours. Within 15 minutes the samples were centrifuged at 4°C for 10 minutes at 1500 rpm to separate the plasma and serum. Plasma and serum were stored at -80°C until further processing.

2.3. Biochemical analysis

Blood samples were analyzed to determine the levels of vitamin B12, folic acid and iron. Vitamin B12 levels were detected by using a serum B12 assay through electro-

chemiluminescence immunoassay (ECLIA). Folic acid levels were determined by a serum folate assay using radioimmunoassay (RIA). Iron levels were assessed using the Serum Iron Test (Colorimetric Method). Participants with values below the reference range were considered deficient.

2.4. Academic performance evaluation

Exam data was collected from participants' previous exam results in subjects such as Mathematics, Science, and English. Additionally, teachers completed a questionnaire, rating students based on their attention span, classroom participation, and overall performance. Further, arithmetic tests, reading comprehension and memory recall tests were conducted to evaluate academic performance.

Table 2.1: Parameters Used for Academic Performance Evaluation

Test Name	Purpose / Skill Assessed	Test Description	Time Duration	Scoring Criteria	Maximum Score
Arithmetic Proficiency Test	Assessment of mathematical problem-solving skills	Worksheet containing arithmetic problems covering addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, and fractions	20 minutes	1 point awarded for each correct response	5
Reading Comprehension Test	Evaluation of reading comprehension and recall ability	A 150-word passage read silently, followed by 10 multiple-choice questions assessing comprehension	5 minutes (reading)	1 point awarded for each correct answer	10
Memory Recall Test	Assessment of short-term memory recall ability	Participants viewed a list of 10 unrelated words, followed by a 5-10-minute distraction activity, then asked to recall the words without cues	5-10 minutes delay	1 point awarded for each correctly recalled word	10

2.5. General fitness test

3-Minute Walk test, Push-Up test and standing broad jump were conducted to evaluate the general fitness of the student.

Table 2.2: Parameters Used for Physical Fitness Evaluation

Test Name	Fitness Component Assessed	Test Description	Time Duration / Trials	Measurement Method	Performance Indicator
3-Minute Walk Test	Cardiovascular endurance	Students walked as fast as possible on a flat, marked surface for 3 minutes	3 minutes	Total distance covered measured in meters	Greater distance indicates better endurance
Push-Up Test	Upper body strength and muscular endurance	Students performed as many push-ups as possible within one minute while maintaining proper form (elbows bent at 90°)	1 minute	Total number of correctly performed push-ups counted	Higher number indicates better strength and endurance
Standing Broad Jump Test	Lower body strength and explosive power	Students performed three forward jumps from a standing position; distance from take-offline to the back of the heels was measured	3 trials	Jump distance measured in centimeters	Greater distance indicates higher lower-body power

2.6. Statistical analysis

Multiple T test was performed using Graph pad prism10 to compare the mean scores of micronutrients between the deficient and non-deficient groups. Pearson's correlation was applied to explore the relationship between each micronutrient values and academic performance similarly correlation between each Micronutrient values and overall fitness was also found and represented graphically by selection of 50 students having only one particular deficiency and 50 students randomly chosen from the control group.

3. RESULT

3.1. Demographic characters

Blood samples were collected from participants (n=300) of the control group and experimental groups to check the association of vitamin B12, folic acid and iron on class performance and general fitness among school going children. Different demographic characteristics of the participants were presented in table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Clinical and demographic characteristics of the participants

Clinical parameters				
Characteristics	Girls control	Girls deficient	Boys control	
Chronic fatigue (%)	0	5	1	
Pale skin (%)	0	4	0	
Pale eyes (%)	0	3	0	
Shortness of breath (%)	0	2	0	
Poor appetite (%)	4	13	3	
Demographic characters				
Characteristics	Girls control	Girls deficient	Boys control	P value
Age	11.0 ± 0.5	11.2 ± 0.6	11.0 ± 0.5	1.0
BMI	20.5 ± 1.1	18.5 ± 0.9	20.5 ± 1.1	1.00
Socioeconomic parameters				
Family income (PKR/month)	60000 ± 15000	40000 ± 10000	65000 ± 15000	<0.001
Lifestyle				
Outdoor activity (Hours)	2.5 ± 0.5	1.0 ± 0.4	2.2 ± 0.6	<0.001
Fast food consumption (%)	0	11	0	<0.001

3.2. Vitamin B12, folic acid and iron profile

To assess the deficiencies of vitamin B12, folic acid, and iron in school-going children, various blood tests were conducted of all participants. The serum Vitamin B12 levels, Folic acid, Iron concentration of Experimental groups was significantly high as compared to the control groups (Table 3.2).

Table 3.2. Statistical analysis of vitamin B12, folic acid and iron profile

Parameters	Control Boys (Mean ± SEM)	Deficient Boys (Mean ± SEM)	Control Girls (Mean ± SEM)	Deficient Girls (Mean ± SEM)	P value
NO. of Samples	n=50	n=50	n=50	n=50	
B12 (pg/mL)	274 ±5.50	205±5.17	282 ±11.57	197±5.33	<0.001
Folic Acid (ng/mL)	12.6±0.756	4.71±0.189	11.9±0.623	4.16±0.191	<0.001
Iron (ug/mL)	89.1±3.799	68±1.83	85.6±5.55	54.3±1.88	<0.001

Note: M= Mean, SEM= Standard Error of Mean, p value<0.001

Figure 3.1 (A). Association of Folic Acid and class performance

Figure 3.1 (B). Comparison of levels of Vitamin B12 in four groups

Figure 3.1 (C). Comparison of levels of Iron in four groups

Control boys group: Healthy boys having no deficiency of n=150

Deficient boys group: Boys having respective micronutrient deficient

Control girls group: Healthy girls with normal level of vitamin B12 n=150

Deficient girls group: Girls having respective micronutrient deficient

***Significance at $p < 0.001$

3.2.1. Serum B12 level

When serum B12 levels of both Control (boys and girls) and both deficient (boys and girls) were compared, statistically significant difference was observed between them. The mean and the Standard error of the mean values of serum B12 levels of control boys group and deficient boys group was 274 ± 5.50 and 158 ± 5.17 respectively. While the mean and the Standard error of the mean values of serum B12 levels of control girls group and deficient girls group was 297 ± 11.57 and 179 ± 5.33 respectively (Fig. 3.1, Table 3.2).

Serum Folic acid level

A statistically significant difference was found when comparing the serum folic acid levels of both the control (boys and girls) and deficient (boys and girls) groups. The mean and standard error of the mean (SEM) values for the serum folic acid levels of the control boys group and the deficient boys group were 12.6 ± 0.756 and

4.71 ± 0.189 , respectively. Similarly, the mean and SEM values for the serum folic acid levels of the control girls group and the deficient girls group were 11.9 ± 0.623 and 4.16 ± 0.191 , respectively (Fig. 3.2, Table 4.2).

3.2.3 Serum Iron level

The evaluation of serum iron levels across the control (boys and girls) and deficient (boys and girls) categories demonstrated a statistically meaningful variation. The mean and standard error of the mean (SEM) for serum iron in the control boys and deficient boys groups was 88.1 ± 3.799 and 45 ± 1.83 , respectively. Likewise, the mean and SEM for control girls and deficient girls was 85.6 ± 5.55 and 41.1 ± 1.88 , respectively (Fig. 3.3, Table 3.2).

3.3. Association of Micronutrients

3.3.1 Correlation of vitamin B12 level, class performance and general fitness

A regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between Vitamin B12 levels and class performance among school-going children aged 10-12 years. The model yielded an r value of 0.655, indicating strong, statistically significant positive correlation between vitamin D levels and class performance ($r = 0.70$, $p < 0.05$) (Figure 3.2).

A Pearson correlation analysis revealed a moderately strong positive relationship between vitamin B12 levels and general fitness among

children, $r = 0.604$, $p < .05$. These findings indicate that higher vitamin B12 levels are associated with improved general fitness,

Figure 3.2. Association of vitamin B12 and General Fitness (%).

suggesting that vitamin B12 may play a significant role in supporting overall physical well-being in students. (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3. Association of Folic Acid and Class Performance (%).

3.3.2 Association of folic acid, class performance and general fitness

Vitamin D levels and class performance were found to be strongly positively correlated by a Pearson correlation analysis ($r = 0.700$, $p < .05$). These results imply that students who have higher vitamin D levels perform better

academically (Figure 3.4). An analysis of the correlation between folic acid levels and overall fitness produced a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.737$, indicating a strong positive relationship. This suggests that higher folic acid levels are associated with better overall fitness among children (Figure 3.5).

Figure: 3.4. Association of folic acid and class performance (%).

Figure: 3.5. Association of folic acid and general fitness (%).

3.3 Association of iron level, class performance and General Fitness

Figure 3.6 illustrates that as iron levels increase, class performance also improves, indicating a strong correlation between iron levels and class performance of school going children. The scattered dots on the graph display a strong clustering trend, reflecting that as the iron levels

in students increase their class performance also increases accordingly. Figure 3.7 indicates that greater iron levels are associated with improved general fitness. This conclusion is further supported by the scatterplot, which shows a definite positive correlation between iron levels and overall fitness based on the clustered data points.

Figure: 3.6. Association of iron level and class performance.

Figure: 3.7 Association of iron level and general fitness.

4. DISCUSSION

The study highlights the widespread occurrence of nutritional deficiencies among school-going children in Pakistan. Multiple deficiencies were linked to adverse effects on physical growth, cognitive development, and academic performance. However, the children exhibited no deficiencies indicated a balanced diet practices within the study population.

A notable decline in serum iron concentrations was identified, with a 49% ($p < 0.001$) reduction in iron deficient boys relative to their control counterparts and a 52% ($p < 0.001$) decrease in deficient girls compared to the control group. Pearson correlation indicating a strong correlation between iron levels and class performance of school going children moreover greater iron levels are associated with improved general fitness.

One key factor which influences iron deficiency in children is the consumption of tea on regular basis which is a common dietary practice in many

households. Tea contains tannins which are polyphenolic compounds that interact with dietary iron in the digestive tract to form insoluble complexes. These complexes hinder the iron absorption in the body. This effect is extremely harmful for non-heme iron which is the primary form of iron derived from plant-based foods. Non-heme iron constitutes a significant portion of the diet for many Pakistani children, so regular tea consumption may substantially reduce its bioavailability (Kaya & Aydin, 2023).

Another significant risk factor of iron deficiency is the presence of Helicobacter pylori (H. pylori) infection. Research revealed that H. pylori infection is linked to lower levels of ferritin which leads to an increased risk of anemia (Hu et al., 2016; Saju et al., 2022). H. pylori infection often results in gastritis and diminished gastric acid production which are critical for the conversion of dietary iron into its absorbable

ferrous form. The lack of sufficient gastric acid impedes this conversion which further reduces the iron absorption in the body (Kato et al., 2022).

Iron deficiency is highly prevalent in children of 10-12 years because the elevated iron requirements are associated with growth spurts. Inadequate intake of iron during this critical developmental phase can have profound implications for cognitive development, academic performance and attention span. Furthermore, hemoglobin levels are compromised due to iron deficiency which affects general fitness. Oxygen delivery to tissues is hindered due to lower hemoglobin levels thereby reducing physical stamina and overall well-being (Muhsen et al., 2011). Parasitic infections also contribute to ID especially in the regions with inadequate sanitary conditions and limited access to rich iron foods. Chronic parasitic infections can induce a cycle of malnutrition and weakened immunity which led to poor absorption and exacerbating iron deficiency (Cappellini et al., 2021).

In current study, prominent down regulation of 42% of B12 levels ($p < 0.001$) in deficient boys compared to the B12 levels of control boys and 40% ($p < 0.001$) regulation of B12 levels was found in deficient girls compared to control girls. Pearson correlation analysis revealed a moderately strong positive relationship between vitamin B12 levels and general fitness among children; moreover, research showed that increased levels of vitamin B12 are linked to better overall fitness."

Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency is a significant health concern among children aged 10 to 12 years in Pakistan. B12 is found in animal foods like meat, fish, eggs and dairy products. In Pakistan many children consume diets low in animal protein especially in low-income families due to affordability issues (Fateen et al., 2022). Furthermore, intestinal parasites are highly prevalent in Pakistan which can impair nutrient absorption, including vitamin B₁₂, contributing to deficiencies in these nutrients. Maternal vitamin B₁₂ deficiency during pregnancy can affect the vitamin B₁₂ status of the children that

leads to deficiencies in early childhood which may persist into school age.

Vitamin B12 deficiency often arises due to its impaired absorption in the intestine. Deficiency can result from conditions such as autoimmune disorders, gastrointestinal diseases, long-term medication use (e.g., proton pump inhibitors, metformin), vegan diets, congenital malabsorption, or genetic defects (Green et al., 2017). Boys typically have higher energy and protein requirements due to faster growth and greater physical activity as compared to girls. If these nutritional requirements are not met adequately it could lead to deficiencies in several micronutrients such as vitamin B12 deficiency (Goddard, 2019).

There is evidence which indicates that gender differences in the absorption and metabolism of vitamins contribute to higher B12 deficiency in boys. Some studies have suggested that hormonal differences such as higher testosterone levels in boys may affect the absorption or utilization of certain nutrients. Testosterone may reduce vitamin B12 absorption and utilization through multiple mechanisms. It can influence gastrointestinal motility by accelerating gut transit time thereby reducing B12 absorption efficiency (Singh et al., 2021). Testosterone also affects the expression of transporters like cubilin and megalin which are responsible for B12 uptake in the ileum which potentially reduce the absorption (Müller et al., 2019). Additionally, testosterone may alter liver function and hence impact B12 storage and metabolism. It can lower gastric acid secretion by impairing the release of B12 from food proteins and reducing its bioavailability (Jayasena et al., 2013).

A significant 62% ($p < 0.001$) reduction in serum folic acid levels was observed in deficient boys compared to the control boys, while a 65% ($p < 0.001$) decrease was noted in deficient girls compared to the control girls. An analysis of the correlation between folic acid levels and overall fitness produced a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.737$, indicating a strong positive relationship. This suggests that higher folic acid levels are associated with better overall fitness among children.

A diet deficient in folate rich foods including green leafy vegetables, fruits and fortified cereals is a primary cause of folic acid deficiency. Economic constraints often limit access of families to a balanced diet which lead to inadequate folate levels in children in low- and middle-income countries like Pakistan (Iqbal et al., 2025).

The present study showed that multiple deficiencies adversely affect physical growth, cognitive development and academic performance. School going children skip their breakfast on regular basis that can contribute to deficiencies in iron, vitamin B₁₂ and folic acid. Regular breakfast consumption is associated with better overall nutrient intake including vital vitamins and minerals. These deficiencies can adversely affect academic performance and general health.

Children consume candies and snacks during school hours daily that have indirect effect on levels of vitamin B₁₂, folic acid and iron impacting growth and overall health of students. Sugary snacks are consumed on regular basis which displaces nutrient-dense foods and reduces appetite for balanced meals which ultimately leads to deficiencies in essential nutrients critical for red blood cell formation and neurological function. Additionally, gut micro biota balance is disrupted due to high sugar consumption impairing nutrient absorption, including iron and increasing the risk of iron deficiency anemia (Yilmaz et al., 2018).

Overcooking of food is a most common practice in Pakistani household. Essential micronutrients such as vitamin B₁₂, folic acid and iron are degraded due to prolonged heat exposure. High temperature cooking methods such as grilling and frying reduce B₁₂ content in animal-based foods that increase the risk of deficiency. Overcooking vegetables, especially through boiling, leads to significant folate loss as it leaches into the cooking water. Overcooking can reduce vitamin C in plant-based foods which is crucial for enhancing non-heme iron absorption in the body. Proper cooking techniques can help in maintaining these nutrients and support overall nutritional intake (Spritzler, 2017).

The trend of fast-food consumption is increasing, which is another key factor contributing to essential micronutrient deficiencies because these foods are generally devoid of important nutrients like iron, vitamin B₁₂ and folic acid. A high consumption of fast foods can replace more nutritious foods resulting in insufficient intake of these important micronutrients. This poor dietary pattern increases the risk of deficiencies which can negatively affect the growth, cognitive development and overall health of children (Mumena et al., 2022).

A holistic approach is needed for addressing vitamin B₁₂, folic acid and iron deficiencies in school children in Pakistan. Fortifying staple foods like wheat flour, rice and milk alongside implementing nutrition education in schools and conducting community awareness campaigns are highly recommended. Increasing access to dense nutrient foods, providing supplementation and encouraging healthy cooking methods are essential strategies. Additionally, regular health screenings in schools, training healthcare providers, and enhancing maternal nutrition through prenatal care will contribute to better nutritional outcomes for children, improve academic performance and promote long-term health.

The coenzyme of FA interacts with one-carbon units in various reactions which are essential for nucleic acid and amino acid metabolism within human body. It is necessary for all cellular activities including protein metabolism, improving mental health and reducing depression in children. Additionally, FA is a powerful antioxidant and plays a key role in detoxifying the skin as well as reducing the risk of stroke in children (Mironenko, 2019).

For instance, a study was conducted on schoolchildren in rural India demonstrated that students suffering from iron deficiency scored significantly lower on standardized cognitive tests as compared to their peers who had adequate iron levels (Pradhan et al., 2022). Similarly, vitamin B₁₂ deficiency is linked to decreased problem-solving abilities and shorter attention spans in children which further exacerbate academic challenges

These findings reveal that there is an urgent need for public health measures to address these critical nutritional gaps and promote better physical and academic outcomes in children.

REFERENCES

- Akubuilu, U., Iloh, K. K., Onu, J., Iloh, O., Ubesie, A., & Ikefuna, A. N. (2020). Nutritional status of primary school children: Association with intelligence quotient and academic performance. *Clinical Nutrition ESPEN*, 40, 208-213.
- Alam, C., Kondo, M., O'Connor, D. L., & Bendayan, R. (2020). Clinical implications of folate transport in the central nervous system. *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences*, 41(5), 349-361.
- Alam, C., Kondo, M., O'Connor, D. L., & Bendayan, R. (2020). Clinical implications of folate transport in the central nervous system. *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences*, 41(5), 349-361.
- Alfawaz, H., Khan, N., Almarshad, A., Wani, K., Aljumah, M. A., Khattak, M. N. K., & Al-Daghri, N. M. (2020). The prevalence and awareness concerning dietary supplement use among Saudi adolescents. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(10), 3515.
- Awasthi, S., Kumar, D., Singh, S., Dixit, S., Agarwal, G., & Mahdi, A. A. (2021). Prevalence of specific micronutrient deficiencies in urban school going children of India aged between 6 and 16 years: study protocol for a multicentric crosssectional study. *BMJ open*, 11(12), e046783.
- Aygün, E., Sayman, Ö. A., Yiğitoğlu, S., Sipahioğlu, S., Yurdakul, E., Ertürk, A. E. Y., ... & Şahin, M. (2019). Evaluation of clinical and laboratory findings of children with vitamin b12 deficiency. *J Pediat Infants*, 4, 05-09.
- Bailey, R. L., West Jr, K. P., & Black, R. E. (2015). The epidemiology of global micronutrient deficiencies. *Annals of nutrition and metabolism*, 66(Suppl. 2), 22- 33.
- Banerjee, S., Roy, P., Nandi, S., & Roy, S. (2023). Advanced biotechnological strategies towards the development of crops with enhanced micronutrient content. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 100(2), 355-371.
- Black, D. M., Bauer, D. C., Vittinghoff, E., Lui, L. Y., Grauer, A., Marin, F., Khosla, S., de Papp, A., Mitlak, B., Cauley, J. A., McCulloch, C. E., Eastell, R., Bouxsein, M. L., & Foundation for the National Institutes of Health Bone Quality Project (2020). Treatment-related changes in bone mineral density as a surrogate biomarker for fracture risk reduction: meta-regression analyses of individual patient data from multiple randomised controlled trials. *The lancet. Diabetes & endocrinology*, 8(8), 672-682.
- Brahim El Hasbaoui, Nadia Mebrouk, Salahiddine Saghir, Abdelhkim El Yajouri, Rachid Abilkassem, and Aomar A. Vitamin B12 Deficiency: Case Report and Review of Literature. 2021. the pan African medical journal
- Burrows, T., Goldman, S., Pursey, K., & Lim, R. (2017). Is there an association between dietary intake and academic achievement: a systematic review. *Journal of Human Nutrition and Dietetics*, 30(2), 117-140.
- Cappellini, M. D., & Motta, I. (2021). Anemia in clinical practice—Definition and classification: Does hemoglobin change with aging? *Seminars in Hematology*, 58(2), 111-118.
- Crider, K. S., Bailey, L. B., & Berry, R. J. (2011). Folic acid food fortification—its history, effect, concerns, and future directions. *Nutrients*, 3(3), 370-384.
- Educational Psychology Review, 29(2), 157-170.
- El Ati, J., Doggui, R., Dogui, D., & El Ati-Hellal, M. (2024). Skipping breakfast is associated to inadequate nutrient intakes among Tunisian children: a cross-sectional study. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*, 12, 1427638.

- Evang, E. C., Habte, T.-Y., Owino, W. O., & Krawinkel, M. B. (2020). The nutritional and micronutrient status of urban schoolchildren with moderate anemia is better than in a rural area in Kenya. *Nutrients*, 12(1), 207.
- Fateen, T., Kashif, Z., Ali, S. S., Aamer, F., Ali, K. S., Pasha, M. B., & Warriach, S. Z. (2022). Vitamin B 12 deficiency.... The predominant cause of macrocytic anemia in pediatric population visiting Children hospital Lahore. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*, 16(03), 242-242.
- Goddard, R. (2019). Nutritional deficiencies in children and their impact on health. *Pediatric Nutrition Journal*, 18(2), 234-245.
- Green, R. (2017). Vitamin B12 deficiency from the perspective of a practicing hematologist. *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology*, 129(19), 2603-2611.
- Hu, Y., Chen, J., Li, M., Li, W., Yang, Y., Yang, L., ... & Piao, J. (2016). Study on the anemia status of Chinese urban residents in 2010-2012. *Zhonghua yu fang yi xue za zhi [Chinese journal of preventive medicine]*, 50(3), 213-216.
- Iqbal, J., Begum, K., Zuberi, R., Muhammad, S., Ariff, S., Chauhadry, I.A., Soofi, S.B. and Bhutta, Z.A., 2025. Determinants of Folate and Vitamin B₁₂ Deficiencies in Under-Five Children: Insights from the National Nutrition Survey of Pakistan.
- Jayasena, C. N., Tye, C., & O'Rourke, M. (2013). The role of gastric acid in the bioavailability of vitamin B12. *The Journal of Clinical Gastroenterology*, 47(5), 379-383.
- Kato, S., Gold, B. D., & Kato, A. (2022). Helicobacter pylori-associated iron deficiency anemia in childhood and adolescence-pathogenesis and clinical management strategy. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 11(24), 7351.
- Kaya, C., & Aydin, D. (2023). The impact of tea consumption on iron status among children: A review. *Journal of Pediatric Nutrition*, 15(2), 85-92.
- Kiani, A. K., Dhuli, K., Donato, K., Aquilanti, B., Velluti, V., Matera, G., ... & Bertelli, Kumar, K. S., Saini, A. G., Attri, S. V., Bharti, B., Sankhyan, N., & Bhatia, P. (2021). Assessment of Vitamin B 12 Deficiency and Risk Factors in Healthy Infants. *The Indian Journal of Pediatrics*, 88, 41-49.
- Lam, L. (2017). Folate deficiency and its impact on cognitive development in children.
- Lee, M. C., Hsu, Y. J., Shen, S. Y., Ho, C. S., & Huang, C. C. (2023). A functional evaluation of anti-fatigue and exercise performance improvement following vitamin B complex supplementation in healthy humans, a randomized double-blind trial. *International Journal of Medical Sciences*, 20(10), 1272.
- Lee, Y., & Park, H. (2021). The impact of folic acid on physical performance in children: A review. *Journal of Pediatric Nutrition and Fitness*, 19(3), 225-231.
- Leung, W., et al. (2024). Preventing iron deficiency anemia in school-aged children: Nutritional education and supplementation strategies. *Public Health Nutrition*, 27(4), 567-574.
- Liew, S. C. (2016). Folic acid and diseases-supplement it or not? *Revista da Associacao Medica Brasileira*, 62(1), 90-100.
- M. (2022). Main nutritional deficiencies. *Journal of preventive medicine and hygiene*, 63(2 Suppl 3), E93.
- Masalha, R., Afawi, Z., Mahajnah, M., Mashal, A., Hallak, M., Alsaied, I., ... & Wirguin, I. (2008). The impact of nutritional vitamin B12, folate and hemoglobin deficiency on school performance of elementary school children. *Journal of Pediatric Neurology*, 6(03), 243-248.
- Mironenko, A., & Eliseeva, T. (2019). Vitamin B9-description, benefits, effects on the body and best sources. *Journal of Healthy Nutrition and Dietetics*, 4(10), 88-100.

- Muhsen, K., Ornoy, A., Akawi, A., Alpert, G., & Cohen, D. (2011). An association between *Helicobacter pylori* infection and cognitive function in children at early school age: a community-based study. *BMC pediatrics*, 11, 1-8.
- Müller, T., Ruder, L., & Fischer, S. (2019). Influence of hormones on vitamin B12 absorption and transport. *Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 104(4), 1053- 1061.
- Mumena, W. A., Ateek, A. A., Alamri, R. K., Alobaid, S. A., Alshallali, S. H., Afifi, S. Y., & Kutbi, H. A. (2022). Fast-food consumption, dietary quality, and dietary intake of adolescents in Saudi Arabia. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(22), 15083.
- Nawaz, A., Khattak, N. N., Khan, M. S., Nangyal, H., Sabri, S., & Shakir, M. (2020). Deficiency of vitamin B12 and its relation with neurological disorders: a critical review. *The Journal of Basic and Applied Zoology*, 81(1), 10.
- Pradhan, G., & Meena, R. S. (2022). Diversity in the rice-wheat system with genetically modified zinc and iron-enriched varieties to achieve nutritional security. *Sustainability*, 14(15), 9334.
- Rani, N. A., Arasegowda, R., Mukherjee, P., & Dhananjay, S. Y. (2017). Prevalence of Nutritional Deficiency Anaemia and Its Impact on Scholastic Performance among Undergraduate Medical Students. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research : JCDR*, 11(3), BC21-BC23.
- Sahni, N. (2020). Nutrition odds to even out corona. *Journal of Postgraduate Medicine, Education and Research*, 54(3), 145-149.
- Saju, J. M., Mandal, N., Kham, N. I., Shahid, R., Naik, S. S., Ramphall, S., ... & Hamid, P. (2022). Is *Helicobacter pylori* a reason for unexplained iron deficiency anemia: a systematic review. *Cureus*, 14(9).
- Sanz, Guillermo, Benet Nomdedeu, Esperanza Such, Teresa Bernal, Mohamed Belkaid, Ma Teresa Ardanaz, Victor Marco et al. "Independent impact of iron overload and transfusion dependency on survival and leukemic evolution in patients with myelodysplastic syndrome." *Blood* 112, no. 11 (2008): 640.
- Singh, Ben, Timothy Olds, Rachel Curtis, Dorothea Dumuid, Rosa Virgara, Amanda Watson, Kimberley Szeto et al. "Effectiveness of physical activity interventions for improving depression, anxiety and distress: an overview of systematic reviews." *British journal of sports medicine* 57, no. 18 (2023): 1203-1209.
- Singh, J. (2021). Vitamin B9 in dark green vegetables: deficiency disorders, bio-availability, and fortification issues. In *B-Complex Vitamins-Sources, Intakes and Novel Applications*. IntechOpen.
- Singh, P., Kumar, S., & Patel, A. (2021). Impact of gender differences on nutrient absorption and metabolism. *Nutritional Research and Practice*, 15(1), 23-30.
- Singh, S., Awasthi, S., Kumar, D., Sarraf, S. R., Pandey, A. K., Agarwal, G. G., Awasthi, A., TS, A., Mathew, J. L., & Kar, S. (2023). Micronutrients and cognitive functions among urban school-going children and adolescents: A cross-sectional multicentric study from India. *PLoS One*, 18(2), e0281247.
- Smith, R., Johnson, K., & Taylor, M. (2022). Folic acid supplementation and its effects on energy metabolism and muscle function in school-aged children. *Nutritional Advances*, 25(2), 150-159.
- Spritzler, F. (2017). How cooking affects the nutrient content of foods. Healthline Media, Inc.
- Vogt, A. C. S., Arsiwala, T., Mohsen, M., Vogel, M., Manolova, V., & Bachmann, M. F. (2021). On iron metabolism and its regulation. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 22(9), 4591.

Yilmaz, B., & Li, H. (2018). Gut microbiota and iron: the crucial actors in health and disease. *Pharmaceuticals*, 11(4), 98.

